

Rietveld structural analysis of new Bi-based piezoceramics with morphotropic phase boundary

Akhilesh Kumar Singh*, Rishikesh Pandey and Ashutosh Upadhyay

School of Materials Science and Technology

Indian Institute of Technology (Banaras Hindu University)

Varanasi, India

E-mail: aksingh.mst@iitbhu.ac.in ; Mobile number: 9415619018

Recently several Bi-based piezoelectric solid solutions with reduced Pb-concentration such as $(1-x)\text{Bi}(\text{Mg}_{1/2}\text{Zr}_{1/2})\text{O}_3-x\text{PbTiO}_3$ (1), $(1-x)\text{Bi}(\text{Ni}_{1/2}\text{Ti}_{1/2})\text{O}_3-x\text{PbTiO}_3$ (2), $(1-x)\text{Bi}(\text{Mg}_{1/2}\text{Ti}_{1/2})\text{O}_3-x\text{PbTiO}_3$ (3) etc. have been investigated to develop better alternative of widely used $\text{PbZr}_x\text{Ti}_{1-x}\text{O}_3$ due to growing concern about toxicity of lead. Further, many applications under non ambient conditions, require high Curie Temperature (T_c) such as actuators and transducers for automotive industries, space technology etc. for which Bi-based morphotropic phase boundary [MPB] ceramics have shown considerable promise. The structural investigation of these solid solutions by Rietveld method reveals coexistence of phases in the MPB region and appearance of new low symmetry monoclinic phase. In this seminar, I will present the results of Rietveld structural investigations on the structure of the coexisting phases and phase transitions in these piezoelectric ceramic solid solutions. I will also discuss the results of structural investigations on electric field poled $(1-x)\text{Bi}(\text{Mg}_{1/2}\text{Ti}_{1/2})\text{O}_3-x\text{PbTiO}_3$ and $(1-x)\text{Bi}(\text{Mg}_{1/2}\text{Zr}_{1/2})\text{O}_3-x\text{PbTiO}_3$ piezoceramics across morphotropic phase boundary that reveals significant modifications in crystal structure. The pseudocubic monoclinic phase outside the phase coexistence region in $(1-x)\text{Bi}(\text{Mg}_{1/2}\text{Ti}_{1/2})\text{O}_3-x\text{PbTiO}_3$ undergoes isostructural phase transformation to long range monoclinic phase with significantly larger lattice parameters than that in the unpoled state (4). In contrast the pseudocubic composition of $(1-x)\text{Bi}(\text{Mg}_{1/2}\text{Zr}_{1/2})\text{O}_3-x\text{PbTiO}_3$ transforms to tetragonal phase after electric field poling (5).

Keywords: Bi-based Piezoelectric MPB Ceramics, Rietveld Refinement, Electric Field Induced Phase Transition.

References:

1. R. Pandey, A. Tiwari, A. Upadhyay and A.K. Singh, *Acta Materialia* 76 (2014) 198.
2. R. Pandey and A.K. Singh, *J. Appl. Phys.* 116 (2014) 044102.
3. A. Upadhyay and A.K. Singh, *J. Appl. Phys.* 117 (2015) 144102.
4. A. Upadhyay, R. Pandey and A. K. Singh, *Scripta Materialia* 115 (2016) 71-74.
5. A. Upadhyay, R. Pandey and A. K. Singh, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 100 (2017) 1743–1750.